

Systematic review and meta-Analysis on thyroid function in post-traumatic stress disorder compared to unaffected controls

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Review question

What is the evidence on the relationship between PTSD and thyroid function? Are all hormone concentrations equally affected by PTSD?

Searches

The search strategy will include published studies that will be identified via MEDLINE/PubMed and from the references of retrieved publications. Information from the title, abstract and key words will be used for identifying publications to be screened for eligibility. The systematic search will be based on the query formula "post-traumatic stress disorder AND (thyroid OR triiodothyronine OR thyrotropin OR TSH OR thyroxine)".

Types of study to be included

This review will consider cross-sectional or longitudinal studies that compare thyroid homeostasis in subjects with and without PTSD or before and after onset of PTSD. Studies will be eligible, if they compared TSH, free T4 (FT4) or free T3 (FT3) concentration in subjects of both groups, and if the definition of PTSD was compatible with the criteria provided by the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5).

Condition or domain being studied

Various forms of trauma including warfare, accidents, natural disasters, sexual assault and child abuse may lead to PTSD. Stressors (criterion A in DSM-5) may involve direct exposure, witnessing the trauma, learning about a traumatic event in a relative or close friend or indirect exposure to aversive details of the trauma, e.g. in the course of professional duties. According to DSM-5 typical symptoms (criterion B) include involuntary upsetting memories, nightmares, flashbacks and, after exposure to reminders, emotional distress or physical reactivity. Affected subjects try to avoid trauma-related stimuli like related thoughts, feeling or reminders (criterion C). Alterations in cognition and mood (criterion D) include the inability to recall features of the trauma, negative thoughts and assumptions, negative affect, decreased interest, feeling isolated and difficulty experiencing positive affect. Alterations in arousal and reactivity (criterion E) include irritability, aggression, risky behaviour, hypervigilance, heightened startle reaction, difficulties in concentrating or sleeping. The symptoms have to last for more than one month (criterion F). Symptoms create distress or functional impairment (criterion G) and don't result from medication, substance use or other illness (criterion H).

Increased concentrations of TSH or thyroid hormones are defined as concentrations being higher than in a control group unaffected by PTSD.

Participants/population

This analysis will consider studies that include subjects with PTSD of any cause, as defined by DSM-5, and a control group. Inclusion criteria are availability of full texts in English or German, reporting of TSH, FT4 or

FT3 concentrations in both groups and compatibility with a current definition of PTSD according to DSM-5.

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

The exposure of interest is PTSD. Due to the exploratory nature of this review we will consider all causes of PTSD.

Comparator(s)/control

The reviewed studies should compare thyroid homeostasis among subjects with PTSD and in a control group unaffected by PTSD or, if the study design is longitudinal, in the same group before onset of PTSD.

Main outcome(s)

Outcome measures are concentrations of TSH, FT4 and FT3.

* Measures of effect

In addition to concentrations of TSH and free thyroid hormones the time interval since exposure will be analysed.

Additional outcome(s)

None.

* Measures of effect

Not applicable

Data extraction (selection and coding)

After removing duplicates records will be screened for inclusion criteria. Quantitative data will be extracted from included papers. The data will include number, mean and standard error of hormone concentrations, type of study (longitudinal or cross-sectional) and the interval after the traumatic event.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

The quality of included studies will be assessed with the Newcastle-Ottawa score (NOS). In order to control for small study effects leading to potential bias funnel plots and additional test statistics will be applied.

Strategy for data synthesis

Quantitative papers will be pooled and summary measures will be included in random effects meta-analysis. Between-study variance will be assessed with the DerSimonian-Laird estimator, Cochran's Q and tau squared, and heterogeneity with Higgins' and Thompson's I squared. Calculations will be supported by the R packages meta and metaphor.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

If meta-regression suggests an association of TSH or thyroid hormones concentrations to the time interval after the traumatic event or if a sufficient proportion of studies is from both longitudinal and cross-sectional type, thereby warranting sufficient power, appropriate subgroups will be investigated.

Contact details for further information

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Type and method of review

Meta-analysis, Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

01 July 2020

Anticipated completion date

01 November 2020

Funding sources/sponsors

Intramural funding

Conflicts of interest

Language

English, German

Country

Australia, Germany

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

MeSH headings have not been applied to this record

Date of registration in PROSPERO

10 October 2020

Date of first submission

09 September 2020

Stage of review at time of this submission

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	No
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	No
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	Yes	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	Yes	No

The record owner confirms that the information they have supplied for this submission is accurate and complete and they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information or omission of data may be construed as scientific misconduct.

The record owner confirms that they will update the status of the review when it is completed and will add publication details in due course.

Versions

10 October 2020

PROSPERO

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